

***N*-(2-Phenyl)-2-thioquinaldinamide and its selective reaction with copper. Spectrophotometric determination of stepwise stability constant of 1 : 3 ionic chelate in aqueous ethanol**

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A novel spectrophotometric method of determination of stepwise formation constants of an ionic chelate of copper has been investigated. A general increasing trend $k_1 < k_2 < k_3$ is found for the complex based on Leden's equation in aqueous ethanol. The results agreed well with those obtained by other methods. The $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$, $\log k_3$ and $\log K$ values are found to be 3.44, 4.20, 5.06 and 12.70, respectively, utilizing the present method at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Elemental analysis of the complex and regression analysis of $\log K$ are also reported. The results are compared to show consistency of the thermodynamic stability constants.

Accurate stability values are the main and major research interests and competitive with the current computational methods and their approximate values¹⁻³. A simple and rapid method of determination of the stability constants and distribution of species at the trace concentration requires an absolute warranty of values specially in biological systems. Most of the methods reported earlier are based on extrapolation of functions with limiting concentration of free-ligand both as unbound and a dissociated form.

The reagent *N*-phenyl-2-thioquinaldinamide forms a strong ionic chelate with higher composition stable enough for investigation in aqueous ethanol⁴⁻⁶. A simple and reliable accurate spectrophotometric method of determination of stepwise stability constants based on Leden's equation developed earlier is reported here. The reagent named as IndcoP is known for trace and ultra-trace analysis of copper both in acidic pH (1.6-6.5) and alkaline pH (8-13) medium. The method is highly sensitive, selective, almost specific with masking action and unique in its applications⁷. The excellent agreement of stepwise and overall stability constants (k_1 , k_2 , k_3 and K) obtained by two methods is the major highlight of the title subject and reported results. The chromophoric reagent group exhibits tautomeric forms favourably disposed for chelation giving thermally stable octahedral complex⁸. The results have been compared with other methods and discussed in this paper. The metal is bonded with S and N atoms of azomethine linkage as revealed by the group frequencies for Cu-N and Cu-S bonds in the IR spectra in Nujol⁹ and far IR region. The elemental analyses and other studies confirmed the 1 : 3 composition

with proposed molecular formula to be $H[Cu(TQA)_3]$. The self polarizability of sulphur supported the CT spectra of $Cu \rightarrow S$ bond¹⁰.

In this paper, the spectrophotometric method of determination and evaluation of stepwise stability constants utilizing Leden's equation of copper-TQA complex in 50 percent ethanol is described and reported with regression analysis and compared. The results are found to be excellent and the comparison has been made with two other methods including that of extrapolation and a new conceptual method based on thermodynamic equilibria of the reaction.

Results and discussion

The theoretical molar absorptivity value was obtained by plotting the different absorptivities with varied free-ligand concentration $[L]$ against Y i.e. $1/[L]$, $[L]$ was obtained using Beer's law and mole-ratio data at each step of photometric titrations. The curve was extrapolated and the intercept gave a TMA value of $1.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($8.1 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, Beer's law). Appreciable difference in two absorptivities strongly supports the dissociative nature and overlapping criteria.

In the spectrophotometric method, the plots of ψ functions against free-ligand, $[L]$, have indicated the general trend for dissociating complex with lower amounts of reagent. The β values showed an increasing trend in successive and stepwise formation constants i.e. $k_1 < k_2 < k_3$. This has also indicated the overlapping tendency of the steps in final equilibrium set-up and formation. The dielectric constant of the solvent mixture contributes towards overlap cri-

teria to some extent. On the other hand, dissociation is considered after complete formation of the complex with at least 25-fold molar excess of reagent during equilibrium formation. The results are given in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 1. $\log K$ given by the degree of dissociation, α , is considered after complete reaction with cent percent complexation. Thus, these can explain with great certainty such variation in $\log K$ values at equilibria.

Table 1. Stability constants by the method of extrapolation plotted against degree of dissociation (α) for copper(II)-thiolate in 50 percent ethanol (pH = 2.7) at $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Stability K	$\log K$	$\log K_{\text{extrap.}}$ $\alpha \rightarrow 0$
5.291×10^6	6.724	
5.154×10^7	7.713	
4.331×10^8	8.125	
3.605×10^8	8.556	
9.618×10^9	8.984	13.30
4.408×10^8	9.644	
1.188×10^{10}	10.074	
8.642×10^{10}	10.936	
2.490×10^{12}	12.396	

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K$ vs degree of dissociation : (◆) series 1.

A new method based on Harvey-Manning's equation was utilized to calculate the stepwise formation constant even at trace level concentration. The $\log K$ values thus obtained from the relations, $\alpha = A_m/A_s$ and $K = 1 - \alpha/\alpha^2c$ for a 1 : 1 complex species, were compared to that given by utilizing Leden's equation. The $\log K$ was also calculated using the concept of TMA from the relation $\alpha = A_{\text{TMA}} - A_s/A_{\text{TMA}}$ for the 1 : 3 chelate where A_{TMA} = theoretical molar absorbance. The $\log K$ based on TMA concept is found to be 13.96 which is maximum stability order that can be obtained for the complex. The concentration formation constants obtained from those equations are termed as thermodynamic stability constants and thus, the free-energy change

for the reaction can be calculated.

In the extrapolation method, the different $\log K$ values obtained from corresponding α values in the mole-ratio curve were plotted against α when a linear plot having a negative slope was obtained. $\log K$ values sharply increases with free-ligand, [L]. $\log K_{\text{extrap.}}$ was found to be 13.30 by this extrapolation method have shown excellent agreement with those obtained by Leden's and Harvey-Manning's equation. A difference in $\log K$ values of more than 1 unit once again proved that the polymeric unit of copper(II) thiolate is slightly dissociating in nature. Moreover, formation steps are combined with overlapping criteria and also, under the influence of tautomeric nature of keto-enol form of reagent in absence of sufficient excess in amounts.

Degree of dissociation and stability constants :

These thermodynamic constants were calculated from mole ratio plot $\alpha = A_m(0.515) - A_s(0.335)/A_m(0.515)$, where A_m, A_s are the absorbances with excess and stoichiometric amount of reagent respectively. The instability constant (K') is obtained by Harving-Manning equation $K' = 27 \alpha^4 c^3 / 1 - \alpha$ for the 1 : 3 copper complex, c is the molar concentration ($6.3 \times 10^{-5} M$) of the metal. The overall stability constant is found to be 12.81 ($\log K$). The stepwise formation constants were determined by a novel method based on HM's equation. The k_1, k_2, k_3 values were obtained from molar ratio plot by spectrophotometric technique. The \log values were obtained to be 3.49, 4.42, 4.90 ($\log K = 12.81$), respectively.

After complete of the formation of 1 : 1 species, 1 : 2 species begins to form and then afterwards 1 : 3 species is formed in solution. The CuL_1 is immediately converted to CuL_2 and HCuL_3 complex with excess of reagent. At equilibrium there will be minimum dissociation in the solvent mixture and it becomes highly stable.

For 1 : 1 complex, $K = k_1 = 1 - \alpha/\alpha^2c$, where $\alpha = A_m - A_s/A_m$. So also, for a 1 : 2 complex formed from 1 : 1 complex $K = k_2 = 1 - \alpha/\alpha^2c$ where A_m for the 1 : 1 complex becomes the A_s for the higher composition i.e. 1 : 2 complex. Thus, 0.215 is the maximum abs. for 1 : 1 complex species after which 1 : 2 complex is formed. So, 0.215 is the stoichiometric abs. for 1 : 2 complex and the maximum abs. for 1 : 2 complex is 0.335. Similar is the sequence followed for 1 : 3 complex where the maximum abs. for 1 : 3 complex is 0.515. Hence, abs. becomes maximum for 1 : 1 complex at 1 : 1 stoichiometric composition and it is thus minimum for 1 : 2 complex. Similarly, abs. 0.215 is minimum for 1 : 3 species and 0.335 is maximum for 1 : 3 species at stoichiometric ratio amount of the chelate species but the maximum abs. is 0.515 with excess reagent beyond mole ratio amount. It is quite independent of neutral or ionic

nature and solvent polarity. Only overlapping may result a bit varying trend of the species respectively at equilibria formation. The calculations have been made on the assumption that the complexes are not formed in stepwise continuous manner ($\text{CuL}_1\text{-CuL}_2\text{-CuL}_3$) and there must be a region of stability for each complex formation stage for an equilibrium to achieve. The values will slightly vary if the assumptions are not completely satisfied.

Stability constants :

The chromophoric reagent formed a 1 : 3 (Cu : TQA) chelate measured with pH 2.7 and at 550 nm. A new and novel method has been developed to obtain directly the stepwise and overall stability constants¹³. This is based on Harvey-Manning's equation. The $\log k_{1,2,3}$, $\log K$ values were determined and found to be 3.49, 4.40, 4.90 and 12.81, respectively at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ for copper(II) thioquinaldinamate chelate. These were compared to that obtained by present method to show consistent results. The precision and reproducibility are nearly excellent based on regression analysis¹⁴ and correlation coefficient¹⁵ ($r > 0.8$). The bio-moiety group of the chromogenic reagent to offer increased selectivity, temperature effect, flexibility of pH range, homogeneities and occurrence of species led to high stability and almost specificity of reagent group and the method. The stepwise and overall stability constants have been compared and the results are given in Table 2.

IR spectra :

The solid complex was prepared as reported earlier in pure crystalline form and its IR spectra was taken in Nujol. The IR spectra of reagent and complex appeared suitable for the region $3220\text{-}1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The most useful region for

spectral analysis of copper chelate having Cu-S and Cu-N bonds are known to be detected by FT-IR spectra. But, in the regions 2550 and 1600 cm^{-1} in which S-H, C=N stretching bands usually occur for thiocarbamides and thioquinaldinamide are important for structure elucidation¹⁶. The formation of weak H-bond formed through quinoline ring N-atom and -SH group in the reagent itself is indicative of chromophoric nature. Also, the tautomeric shifts is well reflected from IR spectra. Thus, the complex showed $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ (w) at 3150 cm^{-1} observed in pure ligand disappeared or lowered by 70 cm^{-1} in the chelate complex in IR bonds. A new broad band at cm^{-1} indicated the presence of a weak H-bond occurring with ring N-atom. *N*-(2-Phenyl)-2-thioquinaldinamide named as Indco and a bidentate chelating reagent normally forms a 5-membered stable chelate of copper(II) with either with azomethine N and thiol S or with ring N and thio-keto sulphur as the binding sites in the 1 : 3 chelate. The chelate develops a tendency to polymerize with a highly stable benzene ring structure stacked with layer structure.

Although the complex is one of high molecular weight molecule, the combinatorial access of basic 4-membered unit embedded to a 6-membered cyclic ether structure led to the formation of a thermally stable polymeric unit with stacked layers of molecules. This particular tendency resulted an increasing trend of the stepwise stability constants ($k_1 < k_2 < k_3$). A strong stabilizing energy and force of attraction by the ligand field led to higher composition. Excitation always leads to higher state of configuration and energy configuration. The m.p. is higher compared to reagent only.

Table 2. Spectrophotometric methods of determination of stepwise and successive stability constants of copper(II)-thiolate chelate with *N*-(2-phenyl)-2-thioquinaldinamide in 50 percent ethanol (pH = 2.7) at $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Sl. no.	Method based on equations	$\log k_1(\beta_1)$ $\log \beta_1$	$\log k_2(\beta_2/\beta_1)$ $\log \beta_2$	$\log k_3(\beta_3/\beta_2)$	$\log K$ $\log \beta_3$	S.D.	% RSD	<i>t</i> -test value	Correlation coefficient $r (N = 3)$
1.	Leden's	3.44	4.20	5.06	12.70	± 0.3194	10.65	1.28	0.8132
		3.44	7.64		12.70				
2.	Harvey-Manning's	3.49	4.42	4.90	12.81				
3.	Method of extrapolation of $\log K$ vs α	$\log K_{\text{extrap}} \alpha \rightarrow 0$			$\log K_{\text{extrap}}$ 13.30				

$$t = \frac{|\bar{x} - \mu| \sqrt{N}}{\text{Std. dev. (s)}} ; t = r(n-2)^{1/2} / (1-r^2)^{1/2} \text{ and } k_1 < k_2 < k_3, \text{ where } t = \text{Students } t\text{-test value and } r = \text{correlation coefficient and the terms have their usual meaning.}$$

$$\beta_1 = 2.75 \times 10^3, \beta_2 = 4.4 \times 10^7 \text{ and } \beta_3 = 5.0 \times 10^{12}.$$

The π -bonding nature of the chromophoric reagent greatly influences due to presence of highly polarizable sulphur with excess energy field for selective reaction to occur. The stable coordinating group -C(S)-NH- is bonded to copper(II) as revealed from the effect of temperature. The IR spectra showed that the lowering of N-H stretching frequency (3220 cm^{-1} , m) due to H-bonding in the thiopeptide chain as localized effect^{17,18}. The $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ changes by 70 cm^{-1} and it is quite broad. The absorption band due to -C(S)-NH- is lowered from $1520\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (s) to $1440\text{--}1455\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (s) in the chelate. It has been confirmed from the same observed frequency with absence of shoulder peak (1325 cm^{-1}) at 1375 cm^{-1} (s) that both the keto-enol existed, but reacted selectively based on the solvent and pH of the medium.

Experimental

A Hilger-Uvispek and PE spectrophotometer with 1-cm glass cells was used and values were measured at RT with an ELICO LI-10 pH-meter.

An accurately weighed quantity of copper sulfate pentahydrate was dissolved in double-distilled water and standardized¹³. A 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution in pure ethanol was used. A 0.1 M HCl was used to adjust the pH. All other chemicals used were of G.R. grade. A buffer solution of pH 2.7 was obtained using sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid mixture.

Equimolar reagent solution ($1.5748 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$) were prepared by dissolving the purified. *N*-(α -Phenyl)-thioquinaldinamide obtained by recrystallization from pet-ether in absolute ethanol. Freshly prepared solutions of reagent were always utilized for continuous variation and mole-ratio studies at 550 nm. The solid complex was analysed for metal content by α -benzoin oxime method and elemental analysis by PE analyzer. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a PE 337 spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of reagent : The reagent was synthesized by Willgerdot's reaction. It was isolated following Porter's method²⁰ refluxing pure quinaldine as the main amine part, sulphur and aniline. The pure reagent was obtained by repeated crystallization from alcohol and pet-ether and dried under vacuo. The fine shaped yellow crystals has the m.p. $109 \pm 1^\circ$, the yield was <20% based on quinaldine.

Procedure : To a definite aliquot of standard copper (0–100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) solution, a few drops of 0.1 M HCl were added followed by to 25 ml alcoholic reagent solution (5 ml) and pure ethanol (7.5 ml). The volume was made up to 25 ml with water and contents were mixed thoroughly (pH = 2.7). The reagent blank showed negligible absorbance. The ab-

sorbance of the violet complex was measured at 550 nm against water blank.

Preparation of copper(II)-thioquinaldinamate complex : The copper-thiolate chelate was prepared by mixing copper chloride and the reagent, TQA. 0.17 g of copper chloride was dissolved in 10 ml of hot pure ethanol and the four times molar excess of reagent. The solutions were mixed, stirred and kept for 6 h. Deep violet crystals separated were filtered, washed with water, little alcohol, pet-ether and dried under vacuo. M.p. of the crystal's was found to be $176 \pm 1^\circ$.

Determination of metal : reagent (M : R) composition : An equimolar solutions of the metal and reagent were employed to obtain the composition. Methods of continuous variation and mole ratio²¹ were adopted and a 1 : 3 metal : reagent ratio was found following the recommended procedure. The equimolar concentrations $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} = \text{TQA} = 6.3 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M}$ as the final concentration showed a sharp break at the stoichiometric compositions.

Method of evaluation and calculations : The 1 : 3 copper thiolate solution has been utilized to find and verify the applicability of a new spectrophotometric method of determination of stepwise formation constants in a simple and accurate manner. The plot of absorptivity against $Y (=1/[\text{L}]) \rightarrow 0$ indicated that thioquinaldinamide reagent is highly sensitive with its unique application in variety of matrix field. The intercept gave a molar absorptivity value $1.1 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in comparison to Beer's law value $8.1 \times 10^3\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The most reliable spectrophotometric method developed previously utilized the idea of degree of complex formation as proposed by Leden²². Based on these mole-ratio data were used to evaluate the function ϕ , in the following :

$$\phi = C_M/[M] = 1 + \beta_1 [I] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \beta_3 [L]^3$$

where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ are the successive formation constants and extrapolated to zero free-ligand concentration, $[L]$ and given as follows :

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \Psi_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} (\phi - 1)/[L] = \beta_1 = k_1$$

$$\text{and } \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \Psi_n = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} (\Psi_{n-1} - \beta_{n-1})/[L] = \beta_n = K$$

where $n = 3$. Also, ΔG° or $\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K$.

The stepwise formation constants (k_1, k_2, k_3) were obtained from the intercept values and the free energy change for the reaction²³ was calculated from the relation :

$$\Delta F^\circ \text{ or } \Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \text{ and found to be } -17.57 \text{ kcal}$$

mol at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\log K = 12.70$).

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